

Ergonomic and Occupational Therapy Solutions to Address Issues of Attrition in BPO Industry

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Abstract

Background: Business Process Outsourcing Sector (BPO) sector is one of the fastest growing industrial segments in India. However, the industry is plagued by high attrition rates. Different surveys do indicate musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) and stress related problems by prolonged night shifts and stressful working conditions. To address these issues, there is a paucity of information regarding ergonomic design of the workplace, working conditions, stress and MSD for Indian night shift employees of BPO sector. Secondary data relating the psycho physiological aspects relating to the work is examined to build a context for the present study. The research addresses the issues of impact of violation of circadian rhythm, stressful and anxious work environment, availability of ergonomic work environment design and low job satisfaction of night shift BPO employees.

Methods: Survey data collected in 2011 among the workforce of ten organizations in Chennai is used for this study. The sample study covered 106 employees.

Results:

The output of the research emphasis need for multidisciplinary approaches consisting of ergonomics, occupational therapy and psychology to improve physical and psychological wellbeing of employees to address issues of attrition in the BPO industry.

Index Terms:

Attrition, Business Process Outsourcing, Circadian rhythm, musculoskeletal disorder, Psycho physiological dimensions of work.

I. INTRODUCTION

Business process outsourcing industry is one the fastest growing industries, creating the highest number of jobs in economies across the world [1]. The industry is a human resource and technology intensive. It offers employment for graduates who are repeating given scripts verbatim, without deviation, to that of professional such as engineers, doctors, and qualified accountants who offer high end advice on technical, medical, and financial issues [2]. The

industry's variability, novelty, technological intensity, work intensity, with new sociological and economic networks at the intersection of globalization and liberalization, provide challenging opportunities for researchers across various disciplines especially ergonomics due to the nature of the tasks and performance of tasks. Due to time differences between India and other countries, the workers generally work in night shifts. Russel [3] opinions that they have garnered attention both as a new means of organizing work and as an important axis point from which study of management practices may be initiated. The present interest is like textile mills or automobile factories, which were treated as both objects of curiosity and as metaphors for their age at the time of their genesis. India is one of the major players in this industry with an annual turnover of 14.8 billion dollars growing at the rate of 15.54% and providing employment for 1.5 million persons [2]. The industry growth in India is phenomenal albeit with human resources challenges such as attrition rate of employees to the tune of 40%, which is high compared to other industries across India. The employees are also experiencing low job satisfaction, and health issues ranging from high stress to severe physical illness [1,4].

A. *Business Process and Business Process Outsourcing*

The business process is any 'workflow' that is required for producing an output. More commonly, the term is applied to the production, distribution, or use of information, either on behalf of other businesses or for the clients of such concerns. Business Process Outsourcing in simple terms stated as "the delegation of a business process or workflow to an outside service provider who owns, administers, and manages it according to a defined set of matrices as set forth in a contract [5]. During early stages, outsourcing was adopted relates to repetitive operations such as back office work; later customer service is brought within the realm of outsourcing. The first sector to use the concept is the telecommunication organizations for long distance operators and telephone directory assistance. System engineers developed technical innovations for effective handling of large volumes of customer enquiries with the help of operations research models. With deregulation by governments in different parts of the world, the telecommunications organizations experimented with the call centre model expanding from simple transactions to complex services and sales transactions. [6]. The early research and literature in operations management used to describe the process as a call centre model [7]. The BPO is defined as "any communications platform from which firms deliver services to customers via remote, real-time contact [8]. The contacts are either initiated by customers (i.e., Inbound) or transactions initiated by employees (i.e., Outbound). The employees are provided with

explicit, specific operational guidelines in the form of 'talk time' (i.e., the phrase used in BPO to refer to targeted average call length) and customer interaction scripts. Study [9] found that the scripts generally specify not only the phrases to be used at different points of conversation but also "display rules," that our emotions to be manifested during interaction with customers giving rise to emotional labour giving rise to surface acting causing stress for the employees. Due to technological changes, diffusion has taken place in other sectors and functional areas. Researchers continue to refer to the industry as the call centre industry despite its change in characteristics. Nonetheless, for the purpose of the present research, the term BPO is used to describe the industry. Shift work is one of the most apparent and dramatic components of the work environment. Due to technological changes most of the industries are operating on a 24 (7 mode. This change in the task environment especially in BPO sector modified traditional way of working and paved way for a 24-hour cycle of work and shift work. The definition of "shift work" for present study encompasses work that occurs outside of the typical 8-hour day from 9 am to 5 pm. Examples include permanent evening or night shifts, rotating shifts, and split shifts. The shift work violates biological rhythms especially circadian rhythms. It has been clearly linked to a series of acute and chronic effects on the organism, most of them related to the circadian rhythmicity of the body. The major effects concern sleep, alertness, and performance, but also long-term health [10]. A brief review of these dimensions is needed for further understanding its impact on the psycho physiology of the employees of BPO sector hitherto not addressed in India.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

*“AND GOD DIVIDED
THE LIGHT FROM THE
DARKNESS, AND GOD CALLED
THE LIGHT DAY, AND THE
DARKNESS HE
CALLED NIGHT. AND THE
EVENING AND THE MORNING
WERE THE FIRST DAY”
(GENESIS 1:4-5, KING
JAMES VERSION).*

For all living creatures it is generally believed to live in a regular cycle of light and darkness, that is, the 24 hours solar day. Human beings have the sunlight portion of the day at the time of activity and the dark, nighttime portion the time for sleeping. Periodicity is an integral part of life of humans [11]; circadian

rhythm is the primary category of biological rhythms of interest. The term circadian (Latin: circa, about; dies, a day) was used [12] to denote a periodicity of about 24 hours. Numerous psychological and physiological variables have been found to have a demonstrable 24-hour rhythm, such as body temperature, the sleep-wake cycle, cardiovascular parameters, alertness and cognitive performance, endocrine and metabolic factors, therapeutic responsiveness to certain medications as well as sensitivity to toxic agents, and psychological variables of mood and anxiety. It should be noted that often there is not a simple two-state description of circadian rhythm with a maximum level and a minimum, but instead there is a continual variation during the 24-hour period, with some “peaks” and “troughs” usually coinciding with the natural light and darkness cycle. Although the human body is under the influence of environmental rhythms, such as the daylight-night cycle, it is also under the physiological influence of our own internal biological clock. The synchronization of biological rhythms with each other and with environmental rhythms (external time cues) maximizes our waking and sleeping performance and promotes overall well-being. Night work is opposed to the innate drive to sleep at night and work during the daytime. This unnatural mismatch of environmental and internal temporal influences has been of concern for night shift BPO employees due to the often-disruptive effect of schedule-related time shifts on the normal synchronization of individual biological rhythms with each other as well as with the external time cues. Research indicates that the employees experience lack of sleep, musculoskeletal disorder and stress, thus impacting wellbeing [11].

The satisfaction study [4] for the past eight years indicates that attrition rates in the BPO industry is to a large extent attributed to night shifts, stress and musculoskeletal disorders. It is strongly believed that such kind of problems arise out of violation of circadian rhythm in addition to stress and physical strain caused by task design and work environment design ; this argument is supported by extensive research conducted by different occupational therapists [10].

In addition to the violation of circadian rhythm, it is observed that the work environment at most of the BPO organizations are provided with no ergonomic workplace design relating to best-fit computer mouse design, adjustable keyboard tray, foot rests, monitor arms, gel wrist pads, document holders and task lighting; which are the basic essentials for performing tasks with the least discomfort. These issues are not addressed in any of the research in India and present research identified this as one of the major gaps. Lack of personal identity of employees is one of the most important dimensions causing stress [10]; to cater to the needs of the overseas customers an employee is given a different name, geography and accent makes him live as an American in the night

and Indian during the day according to one of the respondents. The repetitive nature of the job, attending to the customer calls within 180 seconds with an allowance of only 10 seconds to complete the tasks, with no rest time between the calls makes him or her to be highly alert throughout the working time, with a lack of control on the job makes the employee vulnerable to stress and anxiety [13]. Continuous viewing of a computer screen for more than eight hours a day is likely to cause eye problems and frequent headaches. The present research considers this as a major gap to be addressed.

A. Circadian physiology

The psychology and Psychophysiology of shift work is related to the rhythmic timing system of humans. It has its neural basis in the lower frontal hypothalamus, suprachiasmatic nuclei are situated above the optic chiasma. It produces a cyclic oscillation with a period of 24 hours. Although the rhythm is rather stable, it may be modified by environmental synchronizers such as natural light, sleep, food, and other variables.

Figure 1. Melatonin and the Biological Clock (Adopted from <http://www.sleepdisordersguide.com/circadian-rhythms.html>)

Figure 2. The Rhythm of Life

In order to describe the circadian rhythm of individual, frequent measurements are needed – during work, leisure time, and sleep. This need places a considerable burden on the subjects, oral and rectal temperature is considered as a surrogate measure in major studies [14, 15]. The rest activity

patterns are likely to affect the performance of an employee and may be discerned from the following figure 3.

Figure 3. Mean oral temperature of >50 shift workers during the first and fifth night shifts. The 24 hour period with the first night shift began as a normal day with awakening around 07.00 -08.00 after a night's sleep (filled bar) but contains an afternoon nap around 1500(filled bar) . (Figure redrawn from reference16)

Figure 3. Temperature changes and time of the day

This holds true for, among others, noradrenalin excretion, heart rate, and blood pressure. A related observation is the occurrence of ventricular ectopic activity in connection with night work [17]. With respect to adjustment over several consecutive shifts figure 3 suggests that a few hours' delay of the nightly fall of oral temperature has occurred by the fifth night shift. Still, the minimum occurs at the same time as during the first night shift. If at all present, the adjustment over the five-night shifts is considered only marginally. The same pattern has been observed in many other studies [15]. It is likely, however, that part of the apparent adjustment is a direct effect of the environment, unrelated to the biological clock but "masking" its output [18]. For example, lying down is likely to reduce body temperature, and activity will raise it, both masking the underlying circadian pattern. It might be argued that the endogenous circadian rhythm never adjusts in shift workers [18]. It may be discerned that endogenous circadian rhythm cannot be masked by having a higher day time sleep. Pilot study among ten respondents indicated that most of the employees have daytime sleep disorders. The reason for the marginal or non-existent adjustment is that the circadian system is very persistent and needs a longer time for adjustment than night shift employees ever enjoy since they usually revert to a diurnal life when off duty. They do not sleep completely in the daytime as they attend basic domestic and other activities. This is likely to impact the daytime sleep of BPO employees causing different physiological changes. Laboratory studies allow a much better control of environmental influences and make it easier to carry out around-the-clock measurements.

In one of the classic studies [19] showed that oral temperature across 12 consecutive night shifts flattened but never completely adjusted. Similar results have supported the argument are published [20, 21]. It is observed that in these studies all environmental synchronizers (light, food, and social life) were geared towards a non-nocturnal life or daytime life. This is something the night shift employee has low chances to experience. It should be emphasized that most of the studies of the physiological circadian rhythms of shift workers are mainly of theoretical interest. Since, a clear relation between rhythm adjustment and health parameters has seldom been demonstrated, except for a few studies suggesting that individuals who have difficulties tolerating shift work may have desynchronized rhythms or small amplitudes of their endogenous rhythms [22]. Based on these research inputs, questionnaire has been designed to find, number of houses of sheep during daytime, frequency of occurrences issues such as isolation of workplace, concentration, chronic fatigue, and insomnia and depression in the work environment. The high frequency occurrences may provide a cue to lack of job satisfaction due to physiological conditions.

B. Sleep

Disturbed sleep is one of the effects of shift work. Several survey studies have indicated that night shift employees have difficulties, at maintaining sleep after the night shift [23]. The standard approach to study sleeps usually involves recording sleep stages at different time intervals [24]. Sleep studies of night shift employees have mostly been carried out in the laboratory [23]. Some studies of night shift employee's sleep have been made in the workers' natural sleeping environment [25, 26]. The results are largely conclusive in that sleep length of the night and morning shifts of night shift employees are reduced by me to 4 hours. This reduction mainly affects different stages of sleep. While generally recommended sleep is 7 – 8 hours for an adult there is a need to study the daytime sleeping hours of night shift employees.

C. Musculoskeletal Disorders

The causes of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) in occupational medicine and its relation to work have attracted wide attention [27]. It is considered as a major source of disability and lost work time [28]. It has been shown that it is the cause absence from work, [29, 30] and researchers of the present research strongly believe that such issues prevail among BPO employees supported by extensive research [4]; It accounted for 40% of the work-related health costs worldwide [30]. The work-related causes, of MSD, have been studied and documented extensively [27,30,32]. There is evidence that MSD is caused by poor posture, tiring positions, vibrations or

highly repetitive movements [27]. Besides psychosocial work demands, and occupational strains were studied in relation to MSD. In particular, the present study work-related psychosocial factors such as time pressure or rather a fast pace of work, monotonous tasks, low job control, low job satisfaction, lack of social support at work, high workload or even work overload in terms of volume, and perceived job stress as well as psychosocial distress in general have been identified and studied in the present research. There is consensus among researchers that MSD related to the physical aspects of work and strenuous working conditions are on the decline, while those related to stress, excessive work demands, and other psychosocial work factors are increasing. This has been identified as a major dimension to be studied in the present research.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research gap

Following are the research gaps identified for the present study.

1. There is a paucity of information regarding work environment and frequency of occurrence of critical incidents relating to work environment with respect to night shift BPO employees; major critical incidents identified are lack of role clarity, role of immediate supervisor, concentration on the job, experience of chronic fatigue and insomnia, irritation and depression.
2. There are no data available on provision of ergonomically suggested office equipment.
3. Discomfort faced with respect to vision, headaches, digestive disorders and ear problems.
4. Attitude towards; tasks, experience of pressure, constant survival and monitoring, loss of personal identity, lack of social support and disruption of family relationships.
5. Intensity of pain felt due to musculoskeletal disorders.

B. Research objectives

Present research endeavours to address the issue of attrition from the ergonomic and psycho physiological approach and provide appropriate suggestions.

C. Research Design

The research design selected is a cross sectional based on descriptive methodology leading to conclusions. For the purpose of ergonomic and psycho physiological approach secondary data analysis is undertaken.

D. Sources of Data

Secondary sources of data are obtained from different sources and given in the reference section. Primary data are collected from selected ten BPO firms based on convenience sampling.

E. Instrument Design

The instrument consists of five parts; the first part consists of demographic and work-related physiological characteristics. The second part consists of data with respect to work environment and frequency of occurrence of critical incidents; the third part consists of attitude towards the outcomes of job; the fourth part consists of availability of ergonomically designed equipment in the workplace and comfort level with eyes, ears and frequency of headaches and fifth part consists of pain profile of musculoskeletal disorders.

F. Sampling

Ten questionnaires are distributed as pilot survey and the instrument is corrected for ambiguous statements and formatting. One hundred and fifty questionnaires are distributed and 106 provided complete information and the rest are rejected for incomplete information.

G. Validity and Reliability of instrument

The reliability is established with the help of ten human resource managers and ten employees working in different organizations and one of the leading occupational therapists in Chennai city. The words used by employees to describe a work situation are adopted for the study. The Cornbach Alpha for work environment measurement is 0.612 and for attitude towards tasks and experiences is 0.757, indicating moderate reliability.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1.
DEMOGRAPHIC AND WORK-RELATED PHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF NIGHT SHIFT BPO EMPLOYEES

	Sample statistic
Sex	
Men	61.3%
Women	38.7%
Marital status	
Married	28.3%
Unmarried	77.7%
Age	
Mean	25.57 years
Median	25.00 years
Standard deviation	3.49 years
Skewness	.978
Q ₁	23
Q ₂	25
Q ₃	27.5
Education	
BSC	21.7%
BA/BCOM/BBA	17%
BE/BTECH	39.6%
MCA	12.3%
Others	9.4%
No of working hours	
Mean	9.2 hours
Median	9.0 hours
Skewness	.823
No of hours of travel and working	
Mean	11.14 hours

Median	11.00 hours
Standard deviation	1.47 hours
Skewness	.699
Q ₁	10
Q ₂	11
Q ₃	12
No of hours of sleep during daytime	
Mean	6.67 hours
Median	6 hours
Standard deviation	1.24 hours
Skewness	-.536
Work anxiousness	
Yes	61.3%
No	38.7%
Awareness of health problems of employees to the management	
Yes	
No	19.8%
	80.2%
Number of years of experience	
Mean	2.94 years
Median	2 years
Standard deviation	2.12
Skewness	1.40

Inference

The majority of the respondents is men (61.3%) with the marital status of unmarried (77.7%). The mean age of the respondents is 25.57 years and with a median age of 25 years indicating that fifty percent of the workforce is younger than twenty-five years. It may be discerned that the workforce is young populated with graduates from non-engineering streams (60.4%). The mean working hours spent by the employees is 9.17 hours with a median value of 9 hours, indicating that night shift employee of BPO work 1.17 hours more than the employees of other sectors. Since travel is an integral part of the working and mostly provided by the BPO organization to the employee, the main travel and work is computed which amounted to 11.14 hours, with a median value of 11 hours. Therefore, the respondent travels two hours to commute their workplace indicating long hours spent on travel. Most of the employees (61.3%) experience works anxiousness, indicating the workplace Eco system not being likely to be congenial. The most important observation is the daytime sleep of the respondent. They sleep for an average period of 6.67 hours, with a median value of 6 hours and a standard deviation of 1.24 hours. The recommended number of hours of sleep is eight hours and the respondents lose 1.37 hours of sleep every day, violating the circadian rhythm. This may lead to the psycho physiological issues as established by research, which need to be confirmed from the perception of respondents with respect to work environment.

TABLE 2.
PERCEPTION OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORK ENVIRONMENT

Work Environment	Mean	Quartiles		
		Q ₁	Q ₂	Q ₃
I am required to work in isolation in the workplace	2.75	2	3	4

I find my role in the job is conflicting and ambiguous with no clarity in the level of responsibility	2.53	3	3	4
I value my supervisor for being good, honest, understanding and for respecting his subordinates.	2.48	1	2	4
I am not satisfied with my job	3.81	2	3	4
I often experience loss of motivation and commitment due to lack of concentration	3.24	3	3	4
I constantly feel tired and have an increase metabolism (faster heartbeat, faster respiration)	2.56	2	3	4
I get disturbed sleep during the day when I work in night shifts	2.43	2	3	5
I constantly undergo chronic fatigue and insomnia	2.81	2	3	4
If someone criticizes me, I get irritated and depressed over it.	2.59	3	4	5

Inference

The respondents are requested to rate on a five-point scale with 1 anchoring to almost always ; 2 often; 3 number of times ; 4 on a few occasions; 5 rarely. While the mean values provide some guideline, the quartiles are considered for inferences to get better insights. Twenty five percent of the respondents work in isolation. However, another set of 25% work in teams. This indicates that there is a segment of respondents who always work in isolation and in another segment work in teams and there is no commonality of work pattern. The conflicting and ambiguous nature of the job is experienced by 50% of employees indicated by median value. This experience of lack of clarity and ambiguous nature is inferred from the observations of employees. Since the Indian BPOs operate with lower employee cost 35% compared to that of BPOs across the world, which operate with 65% employee cost [13], the employees are expected to do multiple tasks with no clarity of tasks performed. However, 25% of the employees have no ambiguity with respect to the job. Fifty percent of the respondents feel that their supervisor is honest and understanding and respects their subordinates, 25% of the employees perceive that their immediate supervisor is rarely understood and respecting his subordinates. Fifty percent of the employees feel dissatisfied about the job while another set of 50% frequently gets satisfied about their job indicating a high level of dissatisfaction with the job. Fifty percent of the respondents experience loss of motivation and commitment due to lack of concentration. Twenty-five of the respondents constantly feel tired and perceive an increased metabolism. Fifty percent of the employees experience disturbed sleep during the daytime due to night shifts and fifty percent of the respondents undergo chronic fatigue and insomnia. 25% of the respondents get irritated and depressed due to criticism of others. The work environment of respondents as described indicates though there are islands of satisfaction and congenial work environment; however large sections of the night shift

employees suffer from psycho physiological issues of work environment.

TABLE 3.
WORKPLACE DESIGN BASED ON ERGONOMIC RECOMMENDATIONS

Workplace design components	No of Respondents
"Best –fit" computer mouse design	49
Adjustable keyboard trays	53
Footrests	16
Monitor arms	16
Document holders	13
Gel wrist pads	0
Task lighting	18

Inference

Best fit computer design mouse and adjustable keyboard trays are provided for the majority of the respondents. Footrests, monitor arms, document holders are provided only for sixteen percent of employees. None of the respondents have gel wrist pads provided in their workplace. Therefore, according to the sample, in most of the organizations the basic ergonomic resources have not been provided except for a very few basic needs like mouse and keyboards.

TABLE 4.
Physical Discomfort Due To Work on Computer

	Frequency of Pain				
	Never	On a few occasions	Sometimes	Often	Always
Blurred or Double vision	58	19	18	5	6
Dry, itchy, red and sore eyes	34	26	26	14	6
Tension stress headaches and other stress disorders	21	19	41	14	11
Digestive disorders	43	27	16	9	11
Heart problems	88	7	6	3	2

Inference

Most of the respondents indicated that they had no blurred vision however a significant percentage of 43.4% had dryness and sore eyes. Tension, stress headaches and other disorders are experienced by 23.6% of the employees often and always. Similarly, digestive disorders are experienced by (18.85%) of the respondents. However, five of the respondent's experience heart problems which may be studied further. Ear problems are experienced by a few of the respondents.

TABLE 5.
IMPACT OF JOB ON SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL BEING

Impact of Job in Social and Psychological Well Being	Mean	Q ₁	Q ₂	Q ₃
I need to be hyper alert for every second of my working on the job	2.89	2	3	4

I often feel my job is boring, monotonous, answering phone calls all day and has no skill variety	2.98	2	3	4
I feel my job is overloaded by not having enough time between calls due to speed up and understaffing	2.77	2	3	4
I have an incredible high work target	2.7	2	2	4
I experience immense pressure in handling difficult and abusive customers.	2.76	2	3	4
I am constantly monitoring by surveillance, and all the calls are being tapped makes me work anxious	3.37	2	4	5
I am asked to work on shifts; long working hours and the work timings are inflexible.	3.15	2	3	5
I regret that my job lacks career opportunities and there are very less prospects for development	3.32	2.75	4	4
I have developed unhealthy eating habits in my course of working	3.52	2	4	5
I think my quality of life not improved after joining the BPO	3.43	3	4	4
My work in a BPO is disruptive to my family relationship	3.23	2	3	4
I feel I have lost my personal identity and accepted a different identity as a BPO employee	3.2	2	3	4
My family life got disrupted after joining a BPO	3.06	2	3	4

Inference

Thirteen statements are identified regarding the impact of job on social and psychological wellbeing of the respondents. The lower value of 1 is anchored to strongly disagree and highest value 5 is anchored to strongly agree and Likert Scaling is used. The mean values are provided, and all values are more than the 2.5, indicating that the distribution of values is more towards agreement towards the negative aspects relating to the social and psychological wellbeing of employees. The quartile values are considered to have better insights. Fifty percent of the respondents need to be hyper alert for every second of performing the job. Similarly, 50% of the employees consider job is boring, monotonous and overloaded 25% of the respondents perceive that they are given high work targets. Fifty percent of the employees experience pressure in handling difficult and abusive customers. Constant monitoring and surveillance are felt by fifty percent of the employees working on shifts and long working hours in the BPO job is felt by respondents. Fifty percent of the respondents feel job lacks career opportunities and develop unhealthy eating habits. 50% of the respondents feel their quality of life is not improved and 25% strongly agree that the family relationships are disrupted, 50% feel that their personal identity is lost and social support is lacking from the job. These trends indicate that the job has a negative impact on the social and psychological wellbeing for at least fifty percent of the employees.

TABLE 6.
EXPERIENCE OF PAIN AND MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS

Parts of the human body	Quartiles			
	Mean	Q ₁	Q ₂	Q ₃
Left shoulder & Arm	2.22	1	2	3
Left Elbow & forearm	1.62	1	1	2
Left Waist & Hand	2	1	2	3
Left thigh & knee	2.24	2	2	3
Left leg & foot	2.58	1.75	3	3
Head & Neck	3.13	2	3	4
Right shoulder & Arm	2.53	1	3	3
Right elbow & shoulder	2.09	1	2	3
Lower back	2.71	2	3	3
Right wrist & hand	2.38	1	3	3
Right thigh & knee	2.43	1.75	2	3
Hip	2.69	2	3	3
Leg & foot	1.84	1	1	2.25

Inference

Musculoskeletal problems are anchored with the number 1 indicating no pain; 2 mild pains; 3 moderate pains; 4 severe pain and 5 unbearable pains. The respondents are also requested to shade the particular part of the body that has higher pain. While the expected profile for a young healthy adult is no pain or a score of 1. The mean perception of respondents crossing 1.5 to 3.13 for different parts of the body indicate the existence of health issues which may culminate into MSD if not attended by occupational therapists. The pain profile indicates higher pain regions in head and neck, lower back and hips; moderate pain is experienced in the right wrist and hand, right shoulder and thigh and left leg and foot. It has been observed by occupational therapists' violation of circadian rhythm combined with the non-congenial work environment; non-conformance ergonomics design of the workplace and poor social and psychological wellbeing cause musculoskeletal disorders [33].

Figure 4. Pain profile of respondents with Musculoskeletal Disorders

V. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

The topic of circadian rhythm, psycho physiological aspects and musculoskeletal disorders and job attrition is not addressed in a dovetailed pattern and present research is only an exploratory study. The samples are non-random. The size of the sample is small, to establish statistically significant relationships. The purpose of the research is to facilitate a meaningful exchange of inputs from ergonomists, occupational therapists and human resource managers, which is seldom happening in the BPO industry in India. Since the sector attracts 1.5 million employees, especially youth, health care of these employees assumes importance. In addition, India is a major player in the BPO sector it is imperative on the part of industry to take the initiative and provide further impetus to research and funding. The employees of BPO sector generally experience lack of concentration, sleep disturbances during the day, fatigue, insomnia and irritability. This may be traced to the violation circadian rhythm. The research establishes that the employees average sleeping during daytime is 6.67 hours; 1.33 hours less than the recommended sleep of eight hours during the night. Though it has been argued that the endogenous rhythm cannot be suppressed, appropriate rest periods in between work are suggested. The respondents expressed that they have to be highly alert every second of their engagement in the work, causing stress. Repetitive nature of the job, lack of career growth, difficult and abusive customers, constant monitoring and surveillance impact the quality of life of employees. Empowering employees and subjecting lesser supervision is likely to lessen the work anxiousness of the employees. Provision of food and coffee for the night shift employees may appear to be an incentive; however, it is perceived by employees that they have developed unhealthy food habits. The social life and support and family life is perceived to be impacted by the pace of work at BPO organizations and there is a strong need for providing time for the employees to participate in social events. Lack of work design according to suggested ergonomic recommendations for long time working with computers is not being followed in most of the organizations and it is strongly recommended for implementation. The psycho physiological conditions, with poor ergonomic workplace design is likely contributing to the MSD, which in the long run is likely to have serious consequences for the health of the employees should be addressed on a priority basis. In conclusion, ergonomics, occupational therapy, with appropriate inputs from psychologists to sensitise the human resources departments of BPO organizations regarding said issues is suggested as a measure to reduce attrition and remain competitive in the long run for the industry.

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APPENDIX A Questionnaire

This questionnaire is prepared as a part of a study relating to health of BPO employees to be presented at an international conference at Indian Institute of Technology, Madras. The study is only for academic purpose and all the information given will be confidential. Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Dr.Prabhakar & TR Yeshwanthi

Age: ----- Qualifications: -----
No of years of Experience in BPO -----

Gender: Male Female

Marital Status: Married Unmarried

Actual number of working hours-----

1. How many hours a day you spend in travelling to your workplace? -----

2. How many hours of sleep do you get in a day? -----

3. I am constantly anxious about my work Yes No

4. Is your company aware of any health problems faced by you?

Yes No . If yes, what kind of action has been taken? -----

5. Please read each of the statements in the tabular column given below, tick the one (5, 4, 3, 2 or 1) that most accurately describes your own experience in your organization. Choose only one number in the table given below.

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Frequently
4. On a few occasions
5. Rarely

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
I am required to work in isolation at the workplace					
I find my role in the job is conflicting and ambiguous with no clarity in the level of responsibility					
I value my supervisor for being good, honest, understanding and for respecting his subordinates.					
I am not satisfied with my job					
I often experience loss of motivation and commitment due to lack of concentration					
I constantly feel tired and have an increase metabolism (faster heartbeat, faster respiration)					
I get disturbed sleep during day when I work in night shifts					
I constantly undergo chronic fatigue and insomnia					
If someone criticizes me I get irritated and depressed over it.					

6. My office is equipped with some of the tools given below: Please tick the ones that are provided in your organization.

Equipment	Tick the one provided
"Best -fit" computer mouse design	
Adjustable key board trays	
Foot rests	
Monitor arms	
Document holders	
Gel wrist pads	
Task lighting	

9. Please read each of the statements in the tabular column given below, tick the one (5, 4, 3, 2 or 1) that most accurately describes your own experience in your organization. Choose only one number in the table given below.

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Agree
5. Strongly Agree

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
I need to be hyper alert for every second of my working on the job					
I often feel my job is boring, monotonous, answering phone calls all day and has no skill variety					
I feel my job is overloaded by not having enough time between calls due to speed ups and understaffing					
I have an incredible high work targets					

I experience immense pressure in handling difficult and abusive customers.					
I am constantly monitored by surveillance and all the calls are being tapped makes me work anxious					
I am asked to work on shifts; long working hours and the work timings are inflexible.					
I regret that my job lacks career opportunities and there is very less prospects for development					
I have developed unhealthy eating habits in my course of working					
I think my quality of life not improved after joining the BPO					
My work in an BPO is disruptive to my family relationship					
I feel I have lost my personal identity and accepted a different identity as an BPO employee					
My family life got disrupted after joining an BPO					
I feel my social support for my job is less after joining work in an BPO					

7. If you experience discomfort in any of the following areas, please tick the box which best explains the frequency of pain.

1. Never
2. On a few occasions
3. Sometimes
4. Often
5. Always

Nature of Discomfort	1	2	3	4	5
Blurred or Double vision					
Dry, itchy, red and sore eyes					
Tension stress headaches and other stress disorders					
Digestive disorders					
Heart problems					

11. Musculoskeletal Disorders

Do you have discomfort anywhere? Yes/ No

If YES, please shade the particular area(s) on the body diagram and mark on the line the amount of discomfort you feel for each body part which uses these words to describe the pain levels:

- 1- No pain
- 2- Mild pain
- 3- Moderate pain
- 4- Severe pain
- 5- Unbearable pain

